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 Sample Name: Proszki

C_Si 9_1 M

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 9.17 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Error %
C K	93.8	0.03	96.6	5.6
O K	2.1	0.03	1.6	9.3
Si K	4.1	0.05	1.8	5.8

/Lukasiewicz 25.02.25/Proszki/C_Si 9_1 M/Full Area 1/

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35.2 Live Time(s): 300 Amp Time(μs): 0.96 Resolution:(eV) 131.6

